

Liposome formulation of a myristoylated antimicrobial peptide derived from Chionodracine: preparation, physico-chemical characterization and biological activity

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Preliminary Experiments on Myr-B formulations

In order to develop stable and monodisperse vesicles with good Myr-B encapsulation rate, the following formulations were prepared, purified by filtration on Sephadex G-50 and characterized by DLS and DELS:

1) liposomes formulated with DPPC, in the presence of 30% of cholesterol (5 mM total lipids) and at a lipids/Myr-B molar ratio 10:1 (Myr-B 0.5 mM). Huge and polydisperse aggregates were observed after the extrusion; moreover, after filtration on sephadex G-50 only 10 % of liposomes were recovered, and quite polydisperse anyway (Table S1).

Table S1: D_h and ζ potential of Myr-B liposome formulation, before and after filtration on Sephadex G-50

Formulation	Pre-filtration			Post-filtration		
	Size (nm)	PDI	ζ_{pot} (mV)	Size (nm)	PDI	ζ_{pot} (mV)
DPPC/Chol	102 ± 2	0.073 ± 0.014	-7 ± 1	-	-	-
DPPC/Chol/Myr-B	891 ± 112	0.753 ± 0.009	-4 ± 1	170 ± 2	0.188 ± 0.012	-17 ± 0.2
DMPC	104 ± 1	0.073 ± 0.019	-11 ± 1			
DMPC/Myr-B	93 ± 2	0.157 ± 0.033	13 ± 1	89 ± 1	0.135 ± 0.020	18 ± 2
DMPC/Chol/Myr-B	-	-	-	151 ± 10	0.40 ± 0.03	3.0 ± 0.5

2) On the basis of these results we decided to use DMPC instead of DPPC, because DMPC displays acyl chains of the same length of Myr-B, and this should favor a better packing of the bilayer.

Moreover, because Chol is reported to reduce the entrapment efficiency of AMP in liposome formulations [1], we tried to prepare liposomes only with DMPC (5 mM) and Myr-B (0.5mM). We obtained monodisperse liposomes with diameters around 100 nm, but, unfortunately, these aggregates were not stable upon time, giving rise to larger systems within 24 hours. (Table S1)

3) We then explored different lipid/Chol ratios, and used the minimum amount of Chol (5%) to obtain monodisperse liposomes that were stable for a few days without limiting the encapsulation efficiency. We tried to prepare liposomes at a lipids/Myr-B molar ratio 23:1, with DMPC (2.6 mM) and Myr-B (1.16 mM). We obtained liposomes with diameters of approximately 150 nm and an encapsulation

efficiency (E.E.%) of 74%. However, these aggregates were not stable over time, giving rise to a high polydisperse suspension within 24 hours. We tried to prepare these liposomes also by the lipid cake method already reported for allowing a better inclusion of lipopeptides into the liposome bilayer [2] but we obtain the same results. The relatively large diameter of these liposomes with respect to the pores of the membrane used for the extrusion, is suggestive of a general phenomenon, observed in many phospholipid/surfactant systems. This behavior likely represents an early stage of the transition from vesicles to micelles mediated by Myr-B. Indeed, Myr-B behaves similarly to a detergent due to its membrane-lytic properties, as already reported in the literature [3] [4].

4) Finally, the optimal formulations were found increasing the lipid/Myr-B molar ratio to 30:1 and reducing the total concentration of both Myr-B and DMPC (lipids 1.9 mM), in order to minimize a possible destabilization of the lipid bilayer by the lipopeptide. The cmc of Myr-B is in fact $5.1 \pm 0.8 \mu\text{M}$ [5], and in these conditions Myr-B is only tenfold the cmc. The detailed characterization of the optimal formulations is described in the main text of the manuscript.

Colloidal stability of liposomes in PB and in 10% Fetal Calf Serum (FCS)

Figure S1: Values of hydrodynamic diameter (D_h , panels A, B and E) and polydispersity index (PDI, panels C, D and F) of liposomal formulation and 10%FCS measured after 1,2,7,9 days. Measurements have been performed at 25 °C. D_h and PDI are the hydrodynamic diameter and the polydispersity index calculated by the cumulants method. Error bar associated to D_h PDI, is the standard deviation of three repeated measurements on the same sample. *For these samples cumulant analysis was compared with distribution analysis by NNLS algorithm.

In the presence of serum, all the analyzed samples are characterized by an increase of polydispersity, therefore size distribution was further analyzed by NNLS analysis. This approach puts in evidence at day 1 the presence of at least two distinct populations, where the smallest one is the most abundant and in qualitative agreement with the size determined by cumulant (between 80-94% according to number ratio, obtained by NNLS- number weighted analysis). The increase in polydispersity is also attributable to the intrinsic heterogeneity of the serum itself (panels E, F), in which by NNLS analysis three populations are found. Liposomes in the presence of serum are less stable than in PB buffer and begin to increase in size from day 5.

From day 5, the polydispersity of samples formulated with CHEMS measured in 10% FSC increases, suggesting a higher stability of DMPC/Chol liposomes.

Figure S2: Values of ζ -potential of liposomal formulation measured soon after the preparation after 1,2,7,9 days. Measurements have been performed at 25 °C. Error bar associated to ζ -pot is the standard deviation of three repeated measurements on the same sample.

Myr-B forced release

Figure S3: Release of Myr-B from liposomes over time at 25°C. The lines only serve as a guide for the eyes.

To evaluate the influence of the different liposome composition on the leakage of Myr-B from liposomes, a release study at 25°C was performed using the dialysis method. The amount of Myr-B released in the diffusate buffer was determined over a period of 24 h.

The release of Myr-B from DMPC/Chol and DMPC/Chol/CHEMS liposomes is very similar in the first 4 hours (Figure S3) with a leakage of 36% and 43%, respectively; on the contrary, in the following period of analysis the release rate of MYR-B from DMPC/Chol/CHEMS liposomes is lower, reaching a 62% leakage after 24h compared with an 85% leakage for DMPC/Chol liposomes. This result could be related to the specific interaction of the lipopeptide with the carboxylic groups of CHEMS and also to the different fluidity of the membrane pointed out by MD simulations.

Simulated systems

Table S2: Lipid bilayers and Myr-B/lipid bilayers systems studied by MD simulations

System	Lipids	Myr-B	Water	Ions
DMPC/Chol	122 DMPC, 6 Chol	-	5680	-
DMPC/CMES	122 DMPC, 6 CHEMS	-	5674	6 Na ⁺
Myr-B DMPC/Chol	122 DMPC, 6 Chol	4	4988	12 Cl ⁻
Myr-B DMPC/CHEMS	122 DMPC, 6 CHEMS	4	4982	6 Na ⁺ , 12 Cl ⁻

Figure S4: Snapshots of self-assembly of Myr-B and the mixture of DMPC cholesterol in water: **A)** Starting configuration, **B)** after 50 ns, **C)** after 150 ns and **D)** at the end of simulations (2 μ s). The DMPC molecules are represented in *line*, the cholesterol molecules and MYR-B are represented in *licorice*. The phosphorous atoms are represented as spheres. Non-water oxygen atoms are colored in red, nitrogen in blue, phosphorous in orange, carbon atoms of DMPC and Chol in silver and the carbon atoms of Myr-B are colored in green.

Figure S5: Snapshots of self-assembly of Myr-B and the mixture of DMPC CHEMS in water. A) starting configuration, B) after 50 ns, C) after 150 ns and D) at the end of simulations (2 μ s). The DMPC molecules are represented in *line*, the cholesterol molecules and MYR-B are represented in *licorice*. The phosphorous atoms are represented as sphere. Non-water oxygen atoms are colored in red, nitrogen in blue, phosphorous in orange, carbon atoms of DMPC and Chol in silver and the carbon atoms of Myr-B are colored in green.

Figure S6: Mass density profiles across the lipid bilayer of phosphorous atoms (orange line), water molecules (cyan line) and sterol atoms (black line) calculated from the three independent MD simulation of DMPC/Chol (A, C and E) and DMPC/CHEMS (B, D and F). The mass densities are calculated with respect to the center of mass of bilayer ($z = 0$).

Figure S7: Mass density profiles across the lipid bilayer of phosphorous atoms (orange line), water molecules (cyan line) and peptide atoms (green line) calculated from the three independent MD simulation of Myr-B in DMPC/Chol (A, C and E) and in DMPC/CHEMS (B, D and F). The mass densities are calculated with respect to the center of mass of bilayer ($z = 0$).

Table S3: Occupancy of the contacts between Myr-B and Chol molecules. Average occupancies of the contacts are calculated on the last 1 μ s of trajectories and reported as percentage of simulation time.

Myr-B Molecule	Sim I	Sim II	Sim III
1	0.1	18.8	0.0
2	54.8	0.9	12.9
3	61.9	1.6	29.6
4	0.7	43.0	7.7

Table S4: Occupancy of the contacts between Myr-B and CHEMS molecules. Average occupancies of the contacts are calculated on the last 1 μ s of trajectories and reported as percentage of simulation time.

Myr-B Molecule	Sim I	Sim II	Sim III
1	45.6	100	79.1
2	93.5	100	98.5
3	6.7	30.9	27.7
4	100.0	98.7	100

Biological results

LIVE and DEAD fluorescent assay

Figure S8: LIVE/DEAD images of A) *C. albicans* treated with Myr-B, Myr-B-loaded -liposomes or untreated. Images were taken at 20x magnification, the scale bar placed in the right-bottom corresponds to 200 μ m.

Figure S9: LIVE/DEAD images of **B)** *C. tropicalis* treated with Myr-B, Myr-B-loaded -liposomes or untreated. Images were taken at 20x magnification, the scale bar placed in the right-bottom corresponds to 200 μ m.

Figure S10: Area coverage relative to total area of acquired fields in LIVE/DEAD images of **A)** *C. albicans* and **B)** *C. tropicalis*.

In-vivo toxicity evaluation on Galleria mellonella animal model

Figure S10: Survival curve of *in-vivo* toxicity assessment on *Galleria mellonella* larvae of Myr-B, DMPC/Chol, DMPC/Chol/CHMES and Myr-B encapsulated formulations.

Experimental Section

Material

Dimyristoyl-*sn*-glycero-3-phosphocholine (DMPC, purity >99%) was purchased from Avanti Polar Lipids (Alabaster, AL) and was used without further purification. Cholesterol (Chol), cholesteryl hemisuccinate (CHEMS) and Sephadex G-50 fine resin were purchased from Merck. The antimicrobial peptide Myr-B (Myr-WRGITKVVKKV) was purchased from CASLO ApS, c/o Technical University of Denmark, with a purity >98%. Organic solvents were purchased from VWR. All aqueous solutions were prepared using ultrapure MilliQ water produced by a Millipore DirectQ3 apparatus. Phosphate buffer solution (10 mM) was prepared by dissolving sodium dihydrogenphosphate and disodium hydrogenphosphate dodecahydrate in water and adjusting the pH to 7.4 with a sodium hydroxide solution. Dialysis membrane spectra/por Biotech (cut off 300 Kda, 31 mm width) was supplied by Spectrum Lab.

Preparation of empty and Myr-B loaded liposomes

Liposomes were prepared according to two methods: the thin lipid film hydration method coupled with the freeze-thaw protocol and extrusion[6] (TFH), and the lipid cake method[2] (LC).

DMPC and Chol stock solutions (30 mM) were prepared by solubilising 0.10 g of lipids in 5 mL of chloroform RS. CHEMS stock solution (5 mM) was prepared by the solubilisation of 0.02 g of lipid in 5 mL of chloroform.

The Myr-B stock solution was prepared by solubilising 1 mg of peptide in 2 mL of 1:1 isopropanol/water solution and determining the actual concentration of the solution by UV spectroscopy.

Thin Film Hydration Method

The proper amounts of lipid stock solutions were mixed in a round bottom flask, to obtain a mixture with the desired molar percentage (1:30 ratio Myr-B/lipids). The solvent was removed by rotary

evaporation (Buchi rotavapor R-210; Buchi Vacuum controller V-800 R-200) and the lipid film was dried under high vacuum overnight to remove residual traces of organic solvents. The lipid films were hydrated with the proper volume of buffer solution (10 mM phosphate buffer at pH 7.4) in order to have a dispersion with a concentration of 1.9 mM in total lipids (1.8 mM of DMPC and 0.1 mM of Chol for DMPC/Chol and 1.8 mM of DMPC, 0.08 mM of Chol and 0.02 mM of CHEMS for DMPC/Chol/CHEMS) and 66 μ M Myr-B. The suspension of Large Multilamellar Vesicles (MLVs) was subjected to six freeze-thaw cycles from liquid nitrogen temperature to 35 °C and finally extruded 10 times through a polycarbonate membrane (Whatman Nucleopore with pore size of 100 nm) using a 2.5 mL Extruder (Lipex Biomembranes Inc., Vancouver, Canada).

Lipid Cake Method

The proper amounts of lipid stock solutions (290 μ L of DMPC and 14 μ L of Chol for DMPC/Chol liposomes and 290 μ L of DMPC, 11 μ L of Chol and 20 μ L of CHEMS for DMPC/Chol/CHEMS liposomes) were mixed in a round bottom flask. For Myr-B loaded liposomes, the proper amount of a lipopeptide solution was added in order to have a 1:30 Myr-B/lipids ratio and 3 mL of water and 700 mL of isopropanol were added to the suspension. After sonication (ultrasonic bath Branson 2200) for a few minutes the resulting emulsion was frozen in liquid nitrogen and lyophilised (Martin Christ, alpha 1-2 LD PLUS) overnight at – 54 °C until a lipid cake was formed. The cake was hydrated with buffer (10 mM phosphate buffer at pH 7.4) to obtain a suspension with a concentration of 1.9 mM in total lipids (1.8 mM of DMPC and 0.1 mM of Chol and 1.8 mM of DMPC, 0.08 mM of Chol and 0.02 mM of CHEMS) and 66 μ M in Myr-B. After vortex-mixing for 5 minutes, the MLVs suspension was extruded 10 times through a polycarbonate membrane (Whatman Nucleopore with pore size of 100 nm) using a 2.5 mL Extruder (Lipex Biomembranes Inc., Vancouver, Canada).

Liposome Purification by Size Exclusion Chromatography

Size exclusion chromatography was used to remove the Myr-B peptide not included into the liposomes. A procedure involving dry filtration in a centrifuge and the use of Sephadex G-50 fine resin as a stationary phase was adopted[7].

Size and ζ -potential measurements

Liposome suspensions were analysed by Dynamic Light Scattering (DLS) and Dielectrophoretic Light Scattering (DELS) to assess their mean diameter, polydispersity index (PDI), ζ -potential. Experiments were carried out immediately after preparation and stability of the formulations investigated over time. A Malvern Nano-ZetaSizer apparatus, operating in backscattering (173°) and equipped with a 5 mW HeNe laser ($\lambda = 632.8$ nm), a thermostatted sample holder and a digital logarithmic correlator was used to perform both DLS and DELS measurements. Both size and ζ -potential were measured at 25 °C.

Samples (80 μ L) for DLS experiments were placed in a small-volume cuvette with a 1 cm optical path length without dilution. DLS autocorrelation functions were analyzed by using the cumulant method[8] The first cumulant was used to obtain the apparent diffusion coefficients D of the particles, further converted into apparent hydrodynamic diameters, D_h , by using the Stokes–Einstein equation

$$D_h = \frac{k_B T}{3\pi\eta D}$$

where $k_B T$ is the thermal energy and η is the solvent viscosity.

In DELS measurements, phase analysis light scattering was employed to analyze the Doppler shift and obtain the ζ -potential. Liposomes used in these experiments were diluted to 1 mM with PB (10 mM phosphate buffer at pH 7.4) and low applied voltages were used to avoid the risk of effects due to Joule heating. For each sample, each result is an average of three repeated measurements

Determination of Myr-B Entrapment Efficiency (EE%)

The concentration of Myr-B entrapped in liposomes was evaluated by UV-Vis spectroscopy measurements. The calibration curve was built by using tryptophan (Trp) solutions of known concentration.

Liposomes were broken up before the measurement in order to avoid the scattering due to the presence of vesicles. Briefly, 800 μ L of liposomes were dried under vacuum until the buffer is completely removed, then the residue was dissolved in 800 μ L of 1:1 (v/v) water isopropanol solution. Myr-B concentration was calculated by the absorbance at 280 nm, and the EE % was evaluated by the following equation:

$$EE\% = \frac{[Myr - B]_{ae}}{[Myr - B]_0} \times 100$$

where $[Myr - B]_0$ and $[Myr - B]_{ae}$ indicate the concentration of lipopeptide at the beginning and at the end of the preparation, respectively.

Calibration curve: 2 mg of Trp were dissolved in 20 mL of 1:1 water and isopropanol solution; subsequently, several solutions were prepared by dilution of the stock solution (2×10^{-5} - 1×10^{-4} M) and their absorbance was determined by UV spectroscopy measurements (Cary 300 UV-vis double beam spectrophotometer Varian Australia PTY Ltd., Mulgrave, Vic., Australia, equipped with a thermostating apparatus for temperature control) using small-volume quartz cuvettes with a 1 cm optical path ($A = 4782.7[Trp] - 0.0107$; $R^2 = 0.99$).

Forced release from liposomes

The forced release of Myr-B included in liposomes was evaluated over a period of 24h by UV measurements (FigureS3). Aliquots of 3 mL of liposome suspensions were dialyzed against PB buffer (50-fold excess relative to the total sample volume, molecular weight cut-off = 300kDa Da, membrane 1.9 cm^2), under constant stirring. At predetermined intervals (1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, and 24 hours), the external solution (diffusate) was collected and replaced with fresh buffer. The collected diffusate was freeze-dried, and the resulting residue was dissolved in 1–2 mL of isopropanol to solubilize Myr-

B. The organic solution was then analyzed by UV spectroscopy. The concentration of Myr-B, and consequently the corresponding number of moles, was determined from the absorbance at 280 nm. The percentage of leakage was calculated using the following equation:

$$Leakage\% = \frac{[n\ Myr - B]_{tx}}{[n\ Myr - B]_{t0}} \times 100$$

where $[n\ Myr - B]_{t0}$ and $[n\ Myr - B]_{tx}$ indicate, respectively, the total moles of lipopeptide loaded into the liposomes and the moles released at a certain time x, respectively.

Calibration curve: 1 mg of Myr-B was dissolved in 2 mL of isopropanol; subsequently, several solutions were prepared by dilution of the stock solution (1.5×10^{-5} - 1.2×10^{-4} M) and their absorbance was determined by UV spectroscopy measurements (Cary 300 UV-vis double beam spectrophotometer Varian Australia PTY Ltd., Mulgrave, Vic., Australia, equipped with a thermostating apparatus for temperature control) using small-volume quartz cuvettes with a 1 cm optical path. ($A = 8319.4[Myr-B] + 0.060$; $R^2 = 0.993$)

Morphological Characterization of Liposomes by Transmission Electron Microscopy (TEM)

The morphology of liposomes was investigated by Transmission Electron Microscopy (TEM) coupled with negative staining protocol (JEOL 1200 EX II). 10 μ L of undiluted liposome suspensions were placed on formvar-carbon coated grids and allowed to adsorb for 60 s. Excess liquid was removed gently touching the filter paper.

TEM samples were prepared under four different conditions: the grid was treated with (i) a solution of negative stain, 2% uranyl acetate in distilled water, without fixation; (ii) with fixation in 0.0025% OsO₄ and subsequent addition of 2% uranyl acetate; (iii) with fixation in 0.005% OsO₄ and subsequent addition of 2% uranyl acetate and (iv) with fixation in 3.6% paraformaldehyde (PFA) and subsequent addition of 2% uranyl acetate.

Micrographs were acquired by the Olympus SIS VELETA CCD camera; the average dimension was obtained using the software iTEM (Olympus).

Molecular Dynamics Simulations

The molecular systems were built by using minimum bias approach [9],[10]. Briefly four molecules of Myr-B were centred, with a random orientation, in a cubic box with a side of 8.0 nm and 122 molecules of DMPC and 6 molecules of sterols (Chol or CHEMS) were added around the peptide with a random orientation. The initial structure of Myr-B was obtained after 300 ns of MD simulation in water. All systems were solvated with 5000 water molecules and the appropriate number of sodium and chloride ions were added to neutralize the charges of lipopeptide and CHEMS. The composition of the simulated systems is reported in Table S2. Each system was energy minimized and 100 ps of MD simulation, with positional restrains (force constant of $1000 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1} \text{ nm}^{-2}$) on the backbone of peptides, were performed at 298 K with an isotropic pressure coupling at 1 bar. Finally, 2 μs of unrestrained MD simulation was performed at 298 K and 1 atm with an anisotropic control of pressure. For each molecular system three independent MD simulations were performed.

The peptides were modelled by using GROMOS G54a8[11],[12] force field in conjunction with the GROMOS G54a8-v1[13] for the lipids DMPC. The parameters for sterol molecules were taken from O'Mara et al.[14] The GROMOS G54a8-v1 bonding and non-bonding parameters of the glutamic acid side chain were used to model the hemisuccinyl moiety of CHEMS.

The Simple Point Charge (SPC)[15] model was used for water.

Electrostatic and Van der Waals interactions were calculated using a cut-off of 1.2 nm and the long-range coulombic interactions were evaluated by using the particle mesh Ewald method (PME)[16].

All bonds were constrained using the P-LINCS algorithm[17] whereas the geometry of water molecules was fixed with the SETTLE algorithm[18]. The simulations were carried out with a time step of 2 fs. The temperature of the simulated systems was controlled by coupling the peptides, lipids, water and ions to an external bath at 298 K by using the velocity-rescale[19] thermostat with a coupling constant of 0.1 ps. The pressure was kept constant at 1 bar by using the Berendsen

barostat[20] and in the last 1 μ s of simulation the Parinello-Rahman barostat[21] ($P = 1$ bar, $\tau_P = 4$ ps) was used.

The trajectories of MD simulations were analysed by using the GROMACS analysis tools, VMD v1.9.3[22] and in-house scripts.

The order parameter, S_{CD} , of lipid alkyl chains defined as:

$$S_{CD} = \frac{1}{2} \langle 3 \cos^2 \vartheta - 1 \rangle$$

was calculated by using the GROMACS tool *gmx order*[23]. In the equation ϑ is the angle between a C-D bond of a methylene of the alkyl chain and the normal to the lipid bilayer and the brackets represent molecular and temporal averages.

The time averaged local thickness of lipid bilayers was calculated using *g_lomepro* tool[24] considering the phosphorus atoms of DMPC molecules.

The contacts between Myr-B and the molecules of Chol and CHEMS were calculated using *gmx mindist* tool with a cutoff distance of 0.5 nm. A contact is counted if one atom of sterol is at a distance lower to 0.5 nm to one atom of Myr-B. The occupancy of contact was calculated as the percentage of simulation time in which at list one contact occurs.

Minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC) determination

The minimum inhibitory concentrations of Myr-B free and liposome-loaded were determined by microbroth dilution method, in a 96-well u-bottom plate Falcon (Corning incorporated, New York, U.S.A.) following EUCAST-AFST (European Society for Clinical Microbiology and Infectious Diseases – AntiFungal Susceptibility Testing) guidelines[25]. A suspension of *C.albicans* and *C.tropicalis* equal to 1.5×10^5 CFU/mL were prepared in RPMI 1640 with 2% of glucose (Waltham, Massachusetts, U.S.A.) and inoculated alone (growth control) and in presence of potential antifungal agents in concentrations between 0.97 and 124.16 μ g/mL. After 24 hours of incubation at 37 °C 5%

CO₂ in New Brunswick™ Excella® E24 Series (New brunswick scientific; Edison, New Jersey, U.S.A.), the growths of yeasts were eye-evaluated and the MIC values were then determined.

Live and Dead fluorescent assay

1.5×10⁵ CFU/mL *C.albicans* and *C.tropicalis* suspensions were grown for 24 hours in RPMI 1640 with 2% of glucose in a black Nunc 96-well flat bottom (Roskilde, Denmark), at 37 °C and 5% CO₂. Afterwards the yeasts were treated with MIC concentration of Myr-B and Myr-B liposome encapsulated formulations diluted in RPMI 1640 with 2% of glucose for additional 24 hours. Three consecutive washes with Phosphate Buffer Saline were practiced before performing LIVE/DEAD™ BacLight™ Bacterial Viability Kit (Termofisher scientific; Waltham, Massachusetts, USA) following manufacturer instructions. The fluorescent imaging was conducted with Cytation 5 Cell Imaging Multi-Mode Reader, with an excitation/emission wavelength of 469/586 nm for SYTO9 and 586/647 nm for Propidium Iodide (PI).

Image quantitative analysis

Area coverage was calculated through Fiji ImageJ software (Version 1.53 c) using the auto-threshold tool. The percentage values refer to part of the field, measured in pixels, actually covered with yeast cells (both live and dead) compared to the whole area of the image.

In vivo cytotoxicity on Galleria mellonella

The *in vivo* cytotoxicity of Myr-B free or liposome-loaded was assessed on the animal model of *G. mellonella* larvae. Last-instar *G. mellonella* larvae were supplied by Bugsnack (Foggia, Italy). Larvae with unusual body colour or outside the body weight of 0.2–0.3 g were excluded. All injections were carried out under aseptic conditions using a 0.5 mL syringe, delivering the treatment directly into the haemocoelic cavity via the last right proleg. Prior to each injection, the proleg surface was wiped with a 70% (v/v) ethanol solution (Carlo Erba, Milan, Italy) to ensure adequate decontamination. Each

experimental and control group consisted of 20 larvae. A fixed volume of 10 μL was administered per larva, with tested concentration fixed at 12.5 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$, corresponding to five-fold the highest MIC value recorded for encapsulated Myr-B, which was 2.5 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$. Larvae assigned to the control group received an equivalent volume of sterile 0.9% NaCl injectable solution (Fresenius Kabi, Bad Homburg vor der Höhe, Germany). Following treatment administration, all larvae were maintained at 30°C under aerobic conditions. After the treatments larvae were incubated at 33 °C in aerobic conditions. The viability of larvae was visually evaluated every 24 hours for 72 hours. Lack of mobility after stimulation and melanization were considered as death indicators according to Loh et al. criteria[26]. Cocoon formation was excluded as criteria because the phenomenon was not observed in the 3 days of observational period. Microbiological testing was performed in triplicate and are expressed, where appropriate, as mean \pm SD.

Cytotoxicity Assay against Human Cell Line

The cytotoxicity of Myr-B free and liposome-loaded was determined with the ATPLite Luminescence Assay using a primary human fibroblast cell line (FB789)[5]. The cells were grown in Dulbecco's Modified Eagle Medium (DMEM) containing 10% fetal calf serum (FCS), penicillin and streptomycin at 37 °C in a humidified atmosphere with 5% CO₂.

Briefly, the cells were seeded at a density of 3000 cells per well in 100 μL of culture medium and they were allowed to adhere for 24 hours. Subsequently, 100 μL of culture medium were removed and replaced with a new culture medium containing the formulation to be tested at the appropriate dilution.

After 6 and 24 hours from the treatment, the cells were lysed and incubated with Luciferase/Luciferin solution for 10 minutes in the dark. The luminescence at 560 nm was measured using a microplate luminometer (Victor II PerkinElmer).

As a negative control, the cells were grown in medium, and as a positive control, the cells were grown in medium with 2 % (v/v) NaN₃.

The percentage of cell viability was determined as follows:

$$\% \text{ Cells viability} = \frac{RLU_{\text{Test group}}}{RLU_{\text{Negative control}}} \times 100$$

where RLU is the unit of relative light measured by the instrument.

Haemolytic assay against Rabbit Erythrocytes

The haemolytic activity was evaluated by adding increasing concentrations of Myr-B (from 1.25 to 10 μM) encapsulated in the different liposome formulations and the corresponding quantities of empty liposomes to rabbit erythrocytes (Rockland) previously purified and maintained in Alsever's solution. After removing Alsever's solution by centrifugation, the erythrocytes were washed and resuspended in PBS to the appropriate dilution.

Following, for each concentration tested, 100 μL of erythrocytes solution (at a density of 2.5×10^6 cells/well) were incubated with the tested liposome for 2 hours at 37 $^{\circ}\text{C}$.

After this time, the erythrocytes were removed by centrifugation, and the absorbance (A) of the supernatant was measured at 492 nm.

Erythrocytes were incubated only with PBS buffer as a negative control and in the presence of Triton X-100 at 2 % (v/v) as a positive control.

The haemolysis percentage was calculated as follows:

$$\% \text{ Hemolysis} = \frac{(A_{\text{Test group}})}{(A_{\text{Positive control}})} \times 100$$

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